

1 **TRIP10, TRIP12 and TRIP13 are modulated during senescence and senescence bypass.**

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6 We describe here important changes in expression of the TRIP family of genes TRIP10, TRIP12 and
7 TRIP13 that were a signature transcriptional feature of the senescence program in humans. In two
8 models of senescence, TRIP13 is silenced together with modest activation of TRIP10. Their expression is
9 selectively controlled by wild-type and oncogenic KRas in human cells: while TRIP10 is repressed by
10 wild-type KRas, KRas G12V activates TRIP10. Braf V600E was a strong activator of TRIP12 in vitro.
11 Consistent with a function for genes that serve as central components of the senescence program in
12 transformation, TRIP12 was a highly differentially expressed gene in human melanoma. In an
13 accompanying manuscript, we describe changes in expression of TRIP10, TRIP12 and TRIP13 during
14 treatment resistance in humans with breast cancer that demonstrate the importance of TRIP family gene
15 expression as a component of the senescent state.
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